

POLICING AND COMMUNAL CONFLICTS MANAGEMENT IN IKA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE: FROM FORCE TO NEGOTIATED CONFLICT MANAGEMENT APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined policing and communal conflict management in Ika Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State: from force to negotiated conflict management approach. In the paper, three objectives and three research questions were raised to guide. Descriptive survey research design was used for the paper. The population of this study consists of the population of Ika which is estimated at 102, 456 people. The paper used the sample size of four hundred (200) respondents. The data obtained in this study was analysed using simple percentage. In today's Nigeria, especially in Ika LGA, there is upsurge of communal conflicts which have wasted lives and property on daily basis. One of the principal sources of conflict in the present day is the growing inequality in the distribution of resources among societies and within societies. In managing communal conflict, the Police must shift from the use of excessive force to negotiated conflict management approach. The Police need to rely on negotiation/dialogue as appropriate strategies in managing communal conflict since the use of force as a strategy is not yielding any result. Based on findings, the following recommendations were made There should be adequate training and retraining of the force personnel on communal conflict management approach, how to work in collaboration with community members, respect for human rights so as to win the trust from the public.: There should be negotiated/dialogue management approach to communal conflicts. Police should do away with excessive force.

KEYWORDS: Policing, communal conflict, conflict management, and Ika

INTRODUCTION

The assumption of Herbert Spencer, one of the founding fathers of sociology that all societies in the world would be progressing along one path where political restraint, peace, and lack of internal conflict would be the order of the day, is no longer possible as evidences in the contemporary societies does not support this view (Otite and Ogionwo, 2001). Durkheim in Qadri (2007) said that even a society composed of persons possessing angelic qualities would not be free from violations of the norms of that society. Conflict is inherent in the society as different incompatible interests may have risen among people with different aspirations. At all levels of social life, social conflict in the 21st century seems to be more pronounced than ever just as its toll, in many cases in human lives and misery (Salawu. 2004).

One of the principal sources of conflict in the present day is the growing inequality in the distribution of resources among societies and within societies (Otite and Ogionwo, 2001).

Conflict is healthy for the society since it is designed to resolve divergent dualisms; it is a way of achieving some kind of unity (Charles, 2005). Despite the above observation, the functionality of social conflict in Nigeria, remains destructive and counter-productive to the collective unity, social stability and socio-economic development of Nigerian society (Usoro, Ntepere, Ette, Essien and James, 2019). Conflict refers to a struggle or contest between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals. Conflict is a constant factor in human existence. Conflicts create significant uncertainty and leave many people very unstable. It occurs at different levels which include: intrapersonal, interpersonal, intragroup, intergroup, and international levels. Conflict refers to the conflicting thoughts and actions of various entities, resulting in a hostile state (Alper, Tjosvold and Law, 2000). According to Deutch and Coleman (2006), some of the potential causes of conflict include difference in knowledge, belief and basic values, competition for power and recognition, a drive for autonomy.

Most communal and Intra-state conflicts are associated with natural resources (Umoh and Mbede, 2011:6). Scholars such as Asiyanbola 2007 and Esuong, 2013) have attributed causes of conflict in Nigeria to greed, and power and wealth distribution. Another cause of communal conflict is the natural resources. Resources here refer to oil, minerals, forests, water, gold and fertile land that occur in nature and can be exploited for economic gain (Cocodia, 2008). When poorly managed, distributed or controlled in an unfair or unequal manner, natural resources can also be a major driver of conflict or instability. For Umoh and Mbede (2011), ethnic rivalries including tribal, linguistic and regional differences like boundary disputes and access to land are core causes of communal conflict in Nigeria. For Esuong (2013), prominent conflicts in Nigeria include but not limited to: *Ife-Modakeke* in Osun State; *Eleme-Okrika* in Rivers State (Agwu 2007); *Zango-Kataf* in Kaduna State; *Tiv-Jukun uprising* in Wukari, Taraba State; *Ogoni-Adoni* in Rivers State; *Itsekiri-Ijaw/Urhobo* in Delta State; *Ijaw-Ilaje* conflict in Ondo State. There are also communal conflicts such *Itu-Ikot Offiong* in Akwa Ibom and Cross Rivers, *Ika-Akarika Obu* in Akwa Ibom and Abia State, *Ikot Esu* in Ika and *Ututu Imonte* in Etim Ekpo etc. For Nwoko (2003), the primary cause of communal conflict is dishonesty on the part of the leaders who choose to tell half-truth, paddle outright falsehoods and deliberately distort facts just to suit their selfish purposes.

Failure to manage conflicts is itself ominous to the wellbeing of the citizenry and unmanaged conflicts usually degenerate to worse scenarios like Civil Wars, Inter-State Wars and even World Wars. According to Paul and Brahma (2017), conflict management is an approach that is merely targeted at containing or controlling a conflict when chances for resolution are remote. Conflict management involves approaches used to contain a conflict from becoming dysfunctional. In the past, conflicts were managed and resolved by the elderly and community leaders within traditional structures in which they occurred. The complexities of conflicts characterizing the contemporary world have placed greater demands on police organisations to intervene and manage the conflicts. As police organization grapple with these conflicts, it becomes apparent that they should develop clear and sustainable strategies to successfully manage conflict situations. The police have to do away with excessive force in the course of communal conflict management. The Police must

understand that the world trends for policing and public disorder management have shifted from the use of force to negotiated management approach (Hess and Wroblewski, 2006).

The current variety and severity of communal conflicts in Nigeria constitute serious threat to the security and development of the country. Regrettably, Nigeria is yet to develop an effective strategic national security policy adequate for reducing the menace. She also lacks coordinated framework and programmes for guaranteeing security (Abubakar, 2013). Paradoxically, there is continuous proliferation of security and law enforcement agencies, rapid growth of commercial security companies and community crime control initiatives which have supplemented the efforts of the Nigeria Police. However, due to the absence of effective coordination of the activities of the agencies, communal conflicts management strategies by the police rather becomes ineffective (Akaninyene, 2016).

The Nigeria Police Force is primarily organized for the maintenance of public order, prevention, detection of crimes and arrest of those suspected to have committed crime in the state (Osse, 2006). The force is also organised to protect the life, liberty and property of the people. As the crime level increases by the day with changing pattern, police duties have become more important and more demanding than before as people depend on it. It means that without the police, there would be chaos in the society; and a direct invitation to the Hobbesian “state of nature” where life was not only solitary, but also nasty, brutish and short. Policing has always been necessary and indispensable in all our communities especially in the 21st century where the spread of conflicts is alarming as a result of incompatibility of interest among people, families and groups as they interact. As conflict is a constant factor in human existence, conflict creates significant uncertainty and leave many people very unstable.

In today's Nigeria, especially in Ika LGA, there is upsurge of communal conflicts which have wasted lives and property on daily basis. There is a serious communal conflict between the people of Ikot Udo Community in Ika, Akwa Ibom and Akarika Obu in Abia State This communal conflict started in around 1970 and lasted till today (Assana, 2019). Other communal conflict such as Ikot Oyo village and Ikot Inyangese village, Ikot Akpan Okure village and Utu Ikot Imonte, etc. the above communal conflicts have lasted for years, claiming, many lives and property and leaving many citizens homeless till today.

However, the police that are expected to prevent crime, protect lives and property, enforce law and maintain public order appear to be overwhelmed by the phenomenon of communal conflict. Those that perpetuate the conflict appear to be ahead of the police who only react after the conflict situation (Obi and Ekpe, 2012). Furthermore, the Nigeria Police Force are brutal, exploitative and confrontational in the course of managing communal conflict in Ika. In most cases, the police use firearms on members of the community at slightest provocation. The Police in Ika rely on excessive use of force on the citizens; the Police use stick pins or sharp objects into the private parts of suspects, shooting on the limbs; flogging with whips; beating with batons and with machetes as the principal methods of crime investigation in Ika.

In managing communal conflict, it is expected of the Police to shift from the use of excessive force to negotiated conflict management approach if they are to successfully carry out their duties (Hess and Wroblewski, 2006). The Police need to be transparent to the public and rely on negotiation/dialogue as appropriate strategies in managing communal conflict

since the use of force as a strategy is not yielding any result. Furthermore, inability of the police to resolve communal conflict effectively in Ika, has made government introduce the use of Soldiers at the conflict zones, yet the reverse is the case. Despite the much-purported effort made to improve the national police force, the huge security gap and communal conflicts experienced in Ika over the years still persists. It is against this background that this study was set out on “policing and Communal Conflict Management in Ika Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State: From Force to Negotiated Conflict Management Approach”.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Police, Policing

The police are agents of the state, established and charged with the responsibility of maintenance of order and enforcement of law (Alemika and Chukwuma, 2000). The police force is a major instrument of crime control with the authority to apprehend suspected persons, charge them for criminal offence(s) and present such persons to the court for trial. Police are guardian of social order. As an institution, the police force helps to preserve, fortify and reproduce the prevailing social order, and is hardly catalyst for its change. Thus, when a social order is oppressive, exploitative, and unjust, the police preserve it by suppressing and defusing demand for democracy and elimination of oppression and injustices.

Section 214(1) of the 1999 Constitution provides that:

There shall be a police force for Nigeria, which shall be known as the Nigeria police force, and subject to the provisions of this section, no other police force shall be established for the federation or any part thereof.

The functions of the Nigeria Police force are clearly specified in Section 4 of the Police Act and Regulations (CAP. 359, 1990) as:

Prevention and detection of crime; Apprehension of offenders; Preservation of law and order; Protection of life and property; Enforcement of all laws and regulations with which they are charged; and Military duties within or without Nigeria as may be required of them.

Policing is the process of discharging the duties of maintenance of order and enforcement of law by the Nigeria police force. It is also seen as the activity of making societies safe which entails intentional attempts to regulate the distribution of physical security produced by actual or potential use of force (Odekunle, 2004). The necessity of policing becomes even more evidence in modern societies characterized by diversities and contradiction arising from population heterogeneity, urbanization, industrialization, conflicting ideologies on appropriate socio-political and economic form of organization (Reiner, 2000).

Furthermore, there are conflict management principles adoptable by government through its security agents for communal conflict in Nigeria. The first aspect is to balance the differences, wills and capabilities of the disputing individuals, groups or communities. This could be possibly done through insight into the perspectives of the parties in the conflict situation, especially a sound understanding of the quests of the warring parties. The second principle is to conduct a situational analysis in order to carryout thorough inquiry and

investigation regarding the root causes of communal conflicts. This would unravel the dynamic influences of historical antecedents and cultural affinity responsible for the escalation of the communal conflicts. In addition, the resolution mechanisms would thus become identifiable owing to the detailed understanding of the casual factors and cultural intricacies emanating from the conduct of the situational analysis.

The third principal deals with the exploration of possible role of local actors who may, in some situations, consider the applicability of a customary method which is most often useful in the conduct of a situational analysis. The fourth principle compels the government through its security agents at any communal conflict management to establish an inter-community peace advocacy committee. This would give room for the conflict parties' engagement in interaction leading to their anger and their demands. Also, the committee would provide conflict management architecture that would encourage individuals, groups and communities concerned. The fifth principle holds that the interest of the government as a coordinating mediator should be unbiased. It is expected that government through its security agents be strictly adhere to lines of actions which the parties regard as legitimate, and to which they give consent (Burton 1997).

Furthermore, the police fail in their duties to resolve communal conflict because they not well trained in the area of negotiation/dialogue, rather than arbitrary use of force. Negotiating strategies are not common; it requires proper training and professionalism to understand the root causes of conflicts, those involve, historical analysis of place and how to tackle them in a methodical in order not to hurt opposing parties.

The use of Negotiation/Dialogue and Communal Conflict Management

Dialogue is an instrument which is utilized to foster relationships and build an inclusive consensus among a wide group of actors (Alper *et al*, 2000). It is also used to extend the reach and impact of a formal process through wider participation. Dialogues are structured as conversations and are often public, although specific parts can be conducted in private or confidentiality. The format can range from one conversation to initiatives that are conducted over a longer period of time. The aim of dialogue is to share information, find mutual thoughts, and recognize existing links between different relations and various extents of cooperation (Barge, 2002). The dialogue should be smoothly flexible, according to the context, and conducted within the structure, in the appropriate format and level in order to achieve the desirable goal (Calton, 2001).

However, lack of negotiation/dialogue makes police work difficulty for men and officers of the Nigeria police. So, without strong ties to the community, police may not have access to pertinent information from citizens that could help in crime prevention. Helpful information about historical evidence would be forthcoming from community members once the police establish dialogue mechanism with the communities in conflict.

Dialogue is useful in the pre-determination phase, dialogue acts as an appropriate and robust design to solve complex problem differences and provide the choices and options needed as the basis for decisions (Ifeanyi, 2006). Dialogue act as a bridge for organizational projects, it distinguishes between different aspects such as time, content, and social aspects. Raising awareness of changing perspectives is a fundamental aspect of systematic organizational consulting (Mnookin, 2010). Dialogue creates an environment where people

can see the differences and make decisions based on clear choices and options. Dialogue has contributed to peace and reconciliation conflicts, it has created mobility and visibility and built relationships.

The Police must do away with pride that always make them to be brutal with the citizens, while adhering from to negotiated conflict management approach. Indeed, this approach advocates for a paradigm shift. The idea of negotiated conflict management approach offers a way the police and the community to work together to resolve the serious problems that exist in this neighbourhood. It is through community partnership, the police find that crime-control tactics need to be augmented with strategies to prevent crime, reduce the fear of the crime, and improve the quality of life in neighbourhood (Alemika and Chukwuma, 2000).

Excessive use force and communal conflict management

The Nigeria police are still adopting the traditional style of policing which focuses on arrest and detain with application of force, rather than partnering with the community to find solution to crime and criminal problems. It is regrettably that for nearly a century after its formation, the Nigeria police force still largely retain its colonial disposition as a punitive and expeditionary force rather than a society-friendly law enforcement organ of government. The Nigeria police exhibit high level of brutality on the citizens in the course of managing conflicts in the country. Alemika and Chukwuma (2000) stated that the police are brutal, exploitative and confrontational in carrying in an attempt to manage communal conflict.

The Network on Police Reform in Nigeria (NOPRIN, 2007) said;

.... The police in Nigeria have become a major source of death and ill-health for many people who come in contact with it. Many detainees die outside police custody from injuries sustained during police torture. For instance, an ex-detainee, Ifezina, died in late 2005, several days after being released from Garki police station in Abuja, where he endured prolonged torture that included the repeated inserting of un-sterilized needles into his urinary track. Others leave police detention with injuries that maim them for life or condemn them to a life of physical destitution and ill-health (2).

In a media briefing on 15 November 2007 marking his 100 days in office, Acting Inspector-General of police, Mike Okiro, reported as his principal achievement the extra-judicial killing of 785 persons labelled as “armed robbers” by the police. Four days later, on 19 November, the federal government confirmed Mr. Okiro in the position of Inspector-General, leaving the public with different impression. In 2004 alone, the Legal Defence and Aid Project (LEDAP) documented 2,987 cases of extra-judicial executions by law enforcement agencies. Whatever the explanation, extra-judicial executions appear to have become an acceptable tool of policing (NOPRIN, 2007). Franklyne Ogbunwezeh in (Okoro, 2013) said:

The Nigerian police force is not only a nest of killers, but a sophisticated citadel of corruption, variously manned by cold-blooded murderers. This institution statutorily charged with the maintenance of law and order across the country,

embraced a retrogressive metamorphosis which saw it configuring itself into a notorious synonym for corruption and grotesque incompetence; noted for its arrant desecration of every rational cannon of civilized conduct (123).

In June 2017, Amnesty International issued a report documenting 82 cases of torture by the SARS. Police force uses a technique commonly referred to as “parading” of arrestees, which involves walking arrestees through public spaces and subjecting them to public ridicule and abuse (Nigeria Human Rights Report, 2020). Police use torture to extract confession and information from suspects during investigations and interrogation.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Relative Deprivation - Gurr, Ted Robert 1970

Relative deprivation was developed by American author and professor of political science, Ted Robert Gurr. In his 1970 book *Why Men Rebel*, Gurr explains the link between relative deprivation and political violence. Gurr examines the probability that the frustration-aggression mechanism triggered by feelings of relative deprivation, is the primary source of the human capacity for violence. While such frustration does not always result in violence, Gurr contends that the longer individuals or groups are subjected to relative deprivation the more likely it is that their frustration will lead to anger and ultimately violence.

Theory suggests that people who feel deprived of something essential such as money, rights, political positions, employment, etc would organize or join social movements dedicated to obtaining the things which they feel deprived. In some cases, relative deprivation has been cited as a factor driving incidents of social disorder like rioting, Communal Conflicts, looting, terrorism, and civil wars. In this nature, social movements and their associated disorderly acts can often be attributed to the grievances of people who feel they are being denied resources to which they are entitled. Therefore, the main root of human capacity for violence appears to be the frustration-aggression mechanism; the anger brought by frustration is an inspiring force that positions men to belligerence, regardless of its instrumentalities. The theory discusses the strain or tension that emerges from a disagreement between the “ought” and the “is” of collective value satisfaction which prompts humanity to violence.

Mentioning first formal definitions of relative deprivation, four conditions are required:

1. A person does not have something.
2. That person knows other people who have the thing.
3. That person wants to have the thing.
4. That person believes they have a reasonable chance of getting the thing.

Furthermore, the theory contends that denial and lack of access or opportunities to acquire vital things of life like other persons brings about strain leading to aggression and disorder.

Applying this theory to policing and communal conflict management, one would see that systemic failure or structural defect in a given society couple with denial of opportunities to get well paid job, attain a position of prestige or make wealth like others is significantly connected with frustration and aggression that prompts antisocial behaviour, criminality and violence among people. In contemporary Nigeria, systemic failure manifests in high rate of

unemployment among graduates and non-graduates which correlate of poverty and violent conflicts such as interpersonal conflicts, groups conflict and communal conflict so as to get those things clamouring for. Also, when officers feel this strain without solution, their motivation would be dampened, and frustration would be expressed in brutalizing members of the community for minor or no offence. So, culture of incivility among members of the Nigeria police force is as a result of social strain in which they are experiencing.

METHODOLOGY

The study made use of the descriptive survey research design. The essence was to observe the sample subjects or variables without any attempt to manipulate or control them and to determine the interrelatedness between the variables in formulated hypotheses. The justification for the choice of this research design is that it is suitable for collecting data from a large and heterogeneous population as it is the case of this study. The data used in this study were derived from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected directly from the respondent while the secondary data were sourced from books, journals, newspapers, magazines, seminar papers, government publications and internet materials.

The population of this study consists of the population of Ika which is estimated at 102, 456 people. This population includes none indigenes including security agents in the area. (National Population Commission, 2020). This study used a sample size of two hundred (200) respondents. To obtain the sample size, the statistical formula developed by Yamane (1967) was used as shown

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n = desired sample size

N = population of the study area

e = sampling error taken to be 5% or 0.05 level of significance.

The sampling techniques adopted in the study are stratified and simple random sampling. Stratified sampling was adopted to divide the population of Ika into three clans, and this was done based on the already stratified arrangement. This technique allowed all clans to be represented in the study. Finally, simple random technique was used to ensure that every person; from 18 years and above has equal opportunity of being interviewed. The instruments for data collection were questionnaire and interview schedule. The questionnaire was designed in two sections; A and B. Section A sought to obtain background characteristics of the respondents, while section B sought information that would provide explanations to the topic of investigation. The instrument was designed on a 3-point rating scale of Agreed (A), Undecided (UD), Disagreed (D). The data obtained in this study were analysed using simple percentage.

RESULTS

Question 1: Lack of adequate training and good conflict management approach are the factors militating against NPF in resolving Ika communal conflicts over a long period of time by the Nigeria Police Force?

Table 1: Distribution of responses of question 1

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Agreed	141	70.5%
Disagreed	49	24.5%
Undecided	10	5.0%
Total	200	100

Table 1 shows that out of 200 respondents interviewed, 141(70.5%) agreed that the NPF is not well trained on communal conflict management. 49(24.5%) disagreed, while 10(5.0%) was undecided.

Question 2: Does excessive use of force affect the capacity of the NPF to resolve Ika communal conflicts?

Table 2: **Distribution of responses of question 2**

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Agreed	177	88.5%
Disagreed	22	11.0%
Undecided	1	0.5%
Total	200	100

Table 2 shows that out of 200 respondents interviewed, 177(88.5%) agreed that excessive use of force affect the capacity of the NPF to resolve Ika communal conflicts' 22(11.5%) disagreed while 1(0.5) was undecided.

Question 3: Negotiation/dialogue is a good approach in resolving Ika communal conflict?

Responses	No of Respondents	Percentage
Agreed	183	91.5%
Disagreed	17	8.5%
Undecided	0	0.0%
Total	200	100

Table 3 shows that out of 200 respondents interviewed, 183(91.5%) agreed that negotiation/dialogue is a useful strategy in resolving Ika communal conflict. 17(8.5%) of the respondents disagreed, while 0.0% remained undecided.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding shows that the Police are not well trained to manage communal conflict. Some of the respondents expressed their opinions that some communal conflicts have lasted over a century, and the men and officers of the Nigeria police cannot resolve them. This finding is in line with the opinion of Obi and Ekpe (2012) who said that: the Nigeria police perform unsatisfactory in terms of communal conflict management. The police are ineffective and inefficient in their job of prevention of crime, criminal investigation,

apprehension of crime perpetrators and response to distress call form community members.

The finding shows that parties and communities in communal conflicts do not accept to shift their grounds or relinquish their rights. This is because the police cannot dialogue or negotiate properly. The findings show that order from court is the reason for prolong conflict in Ika. Many respondents said that sometimes, government policies are reasons for prolong communal conflicts. The finding shows that the Police in Nigeria rely on excess use of force in crime investigations, crowd control arrest and in conflict situation. Many respondents said that since the nomenclature “force” is attached to them, so they behave in crime prevention and conflict management. This finding is in line with the opinion of The Network on Police Reform in Nigeria (NOPRIN, 2007) said that he police in Nigeria have become a major source of death and ill-health for many people who come in contact with it. Many detainees die outside police custody from injuries sustained during police torture.

CONCLUSION

The nature and sensitivity of police duties as provided in section 4 of Police Act and Regulations make a police officer an indispensable. Indispensable in the sense that, he is not expected to be just a friend but their counsellor, law enforcer, prosecutor, arbiter and peacemaker The police that are expected to prevent crime, protect lives and property, enforce law and maintain public order appear to be overwhelmed by the phenomenon of communal conflict. Furthermore, the Nigeria Police are brutal, exploitative and confrontational in the course of managing communal conflict in Ika. In most cases, the police use firearms on members of the community at slightest provocation.

In managing communal conflict, it is expected of the Police to shift from the use of excessive force to negotiated conflict management approach if they are to successfully carry out their duties. The Police need to be transparent to the public and rely on negotiation/dialogue as appropriate strategies in managing communal conflict since the use of force as a strategy is not yielding any result. The action lines of the police are basically to mediate the differences and cross-examine the disputant groups, and not

RECOMMENDATIONS

The followings recommendations were made:

1. There should be adequate training and retraining of the force personnel on communal conflict management approach, how to work in collaboration with community members, respect for human rights so as wing the trust from the public.
2. There should be negotiated/dialogue management approach to communal conflicts. Since negotiation is an instrument which is utilized to foster relationships and build an inclusive consensus among a wide group of actors, it should be adopted in conflict situation. Through dialogue information is shared, mutual thoughts are found.
3. There should be a shift from the colonial approach of the use of excessive force since application of force to communal conflicts does not bring desirable solution. There should be friendly disposition among officers so that vital information about crime can be divulged to them through the community members.
4. The law should make provision for people-oriented police force in Nigeria which are ready to exhibit friendly disposition and work with the public.

5. Police should be motivated to do their official job effectively. They need to be equipped and provided with good accommodations and kits for their jobs. Government should paid the police adequately for them to give the best in terms of conflict management.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, M. D. (2013). *Nigeria Police Force: The Journey So Far*. Abuja: Panaaf Press.
- Abubakar, M. D. (2014). "Oga, Pull Over: Time to Reinvent the Police". *The Tell* of March 17, p. 29.
- Akaninyene, S. B. (2016). Inadequate Policing and Criminality in Nigeria. Unpublished Masters Dissertation submitted to post graduate school university of Uyo, Uyo Pp.1-68.
- Albert, I. Olawale 2007. Concepts and methods in Peace and Conflict Studies. In: Bassey, C. and Oshita eds. *Conflict resolution, identity crisis and development in Africa*. Lagos, Malthouse Press. pp. 3–18.
- Alemika, E. E. O. and Chukwuma, I. (2000). *Police Community Violence in Nigeria*. 2nd Ed. Lagos: Centre for Law Enforcement Education and National Human Rights Commission, p. 8.
- Alper, S., Tjosvold, D., and Law, K. S. (2000). Conflict management, efficacy, and performance in organizational teams. *Personnel Psychology*, 53(3), 625-642.
- Asana, S. S. (2019). *History of Ikot Udo Ika and the Creation of Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State*. Sovien Publishers Inc., Lagos. Pp 1-136.
- Charles, J. O. (2005). *Sociological Theory: A Historic Analytical Approach on Man and Society*.
- Cherney, A, and Cherney, A (2018) Police Community Engagement and Outreach In A Counterterrorism Context Counterterrorism Context 5330
- Cocodia, J., (2008), Exhuming Trends in Ethnic Conflict and Cooperation in Africa: Some Selected States, *African Journal on Conflict Resolution*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 9-26.
- Esuong, P. J. (2013). *Security Communication*. Rizavwa Bank of Idea, Abuja.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). *The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria*. Section 214 (1).
- Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette (2006) *National Population Commission*. Abuja: Federal Government Printing Press.
- Gurr, Ted Robert (1970). *Why Men Rebel*. New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- Hess, K. M. and Wroblewski, H. M., (2006). *Police Operations: Theory and Practice*. Thompson Learning Academic Resource Centre, USA. P. 1-513.
- Mnookin, R. 2010. *Bargaining with the Devil: When to Negotiate, When to Fight*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
- Network on Police Reform in Nigeria (2007). *Criminal Force? An Interim Report on the Nigerian Police Force*. Abuja: NOPRIN Report.
- Nkana, N.S., Ekpuk, F. S. and Dode, R. O. (2013). *Citizenship and Peace and Studies*. Chf Print, Uyo. P 1-261.
- Nwoko, U. T. (2003). "Memorandum of Ika Crises: A Comprehensive Chronicle of the Causes, Facts, Issues, and Personalities". Pp.1-63.
- Obi, C. and Ekpe, F. U. (2012). *"The Nigeria Police and the Challenges of Policing a*

- Democratic Society.*” Paper Presented at the 2010 biennial Retreat of the Police Service Commission. Abuja: Police Service Commission.
- Okoro, B. C. (2013). *The Police, Law and Your Rights*. Princeton Publishing Co, Ikeja. pp.1-474.
- Osse, A. (2006). *Understanding Policing*. Amnesty International: Netherlands. Pp 156-163.
- Otite, O. and Ogionwo, W. (2001). *An Introduction to Sociological Studies*. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books, Plc.
- Qadri, S. M. Afzal (2005:2). *Criminology: Problems and Prospects*. Delhi: Eastern Book Company.
- Reiner, R. (2000) *The politics of the police*, Oxford University Press.
- Salawu, B. (2004). *Sociology, Concepts and Themes: An Introduction*. Ibadan: Cresthill Publishers.
- The Nigeria Police Force (2007). *Annual Report of the Force*. “F” Department, Force Headquarters, Abuja.
- The Police Act and Regulations* (1990). CAP. 359. Vol. 20. Laws of the Federation of Nigeria.
- Transition Monitoring Group (2002). Tools and Mechanisms for Civil Society and the State in Conflict Management. *A Coalition of Human Rights, Non -Governmental and Civil Society Organizations*, Abuja. P. 99.
- Umoh, I. and Mbede, I. (2011). *The Force of Peace: Breaking the Circle of Youths Violence*. MEF (Nigeria Limited, Uyo.
- Usoro, N. A., Ntepere, A. C., Ette, U., Essien, E. I. and James, N. N. (2019). “The Youths and Violent Conflicts in Nigeria: The Consequences and Remedy”. In: *Sociology on the Ascent: A Festschrift in Honour of Professor Ekong, Ekong*. Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Uyo. P.416-429.